

Recommended citation: Knowles, G., Clark, R., & Andrews, J. (2019). Herding cats? Reflections on Colleagues' perceptions of learning & teaching in engineering education. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 639-650). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656498.

Herding Cats? Reflections on Colleagues' Perceptions of Learning & Teaching in Engineering Education

G. Knowles

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry. UK

R. Clark

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry. UK

J Andrews

WMG, University of Warwick
Coventry, UK

Conference Key Areas: Managing Change in Engineering Education, Talent Management

Keywords: Change Management, Phenomenology, Staff Perceptions.

ABSTRACT

Set at a time of unprecedented uncertainty, this paper presents a critical analysis of one of the themes to emerge out of a phenomenological study in which 48 colleagues from across one of the UK's largest Engineering Education Departments were interviewed about their perceptions of the Department's strategic direction, strengths, challenges and weaknesses. Undertaken with the specific intention of providing a solid basis for the development and launching of an Strategic Organisational Change Strategy, the colloquially termed *Herding Cats Project* follows an Action Research philosophy embedded within 'Positive Organisational Scholarship'.

In critically reflecting upon the early stages of the first part of the Organisational Change Strategy the paper provides an interpretive analysis of one of six themes to emerge out of 48 qualitative, semi-structured interviews conducted with learning and teaching colleagues from a range of engineering programmes and courses. In doing so it deliberately adopts a positive stance, contributing to current debates about managing change in organisations through allowing Engineering Educators individual voices to be heard and reflected on.

The paper concludes by acknowledging that whilst on the whole the idea of "managing change in academia" is often viewed as an oxymoron with analogies such as 'herding cats' used to describe the nature of the challenge, the formation and

launch of a multi-disciplinary Education Innovation Group (EIG), which has a focus on collegial support, scholarship through empirical investigation and implementation of evidence-based practice, innovation and leadership in learning and teaching, means the time is right to begin to effect organisational change. It is an exciting time to be working with WMG. This paper represents the first of what will be a detailed and empirically grounded account of the issues around effecting change within the UK Engineering Education Sector. Without a doubt, such a debate is both timely and much needed!

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper draws upon the emergent findings of one thematic classification resulting from a phenomenological analysis of 48 interviews conducted within one of the UK's largest Engineering & Applied Science Educational Departments. Commencing by providing a short introduction to the organisational context in which the paper is set, the need for Strategic Organisational Change to be implemented is explained. Following this, the methodological approach adopted with this stage of the Harding Cats Project is explained with particular attention paid to the manner in which the data was collected, coded and analysed.

Whilst six distinctive themes have been identified in the first iteration of the analysis, it should be noted that this paper represents a small part of the initial steps taken under the Change Management Strategy. Very much a work in progress, the findings section concentrates on one single theme, that of colleagues perceptions of the positive aspects of learning and teaching within WMG. Whilst the decision to focus on one theme only was deliberate, the fact that the challenges and problems discussed by colleagues are not discussed here is not only reflective of the fact that the work is in its very early stages but also represents a managerial decision to begin the work by concentrating on the 'positives'. This decision was taken in a purposeful attempt to countermand some of the negativity abound in UK Higher Education & Industry at the moment, primarily as a result of Brexit we find ourselves unwittingly drawn into.

2. BACKGROUND

An academic department of the University of Warwick, WMG is located in the heart of the Industrial Midlands in the UK. Founded in the 1980s, up until recently the Department's main focus was cutting edge Engineering & Technical Research conducted in collaboration with numerous industrial and public sector partnerships. Although research was prioritised, shortly after its inception, WMG began educating future Engineering Managers, offering modular part-time Degrees to UK students from the end of the 1980s. This provision expanded in the 1990s to include overseas MSc Programmes although numbers remained relatively low until a few years ago when changes in the way in which Higher Education is funded over the past two

decades^[2] have resulted in a rapid growth in student enrolments and an unprecedented expansion in the variety of programmes offered.

Now employing over 600 staff, WMG comprises seven research and education centres located on the Warwick Campus in the UK. It also delivers education programmes in seven countries outside of Europe. With a global vision, the Department now has around 1,500 students with 1,200 studying for a full-time MSc on one of 14 different MSc Programmes in Engineering, Applied Science (including ICT focused programmes) Logistics and Innovation Management. In addition to this, WMG also delivers a number of Full and Part Time Undergraduate Engineering Programmes in cooperation with the University's Engineering Department. It also works in partnership with industry to provide a range of Higher Apprenticeships in Engineering, Manufacturing & Health Technology^[1].

Whilst indicative of a successful approach to, and excellent reputation in, learning and teaching, the rapid rise in full time student numbers, from around 400 studying a handful of programmes around five years ago to one-thousand two-hundred and forty students studying full-time on the campus has not been without issue. Unprecedented growth has been accompanied by numerous managerial, practical, technical and educational challenges, the full implications of some are only now coming to the fore as the difficulties of balancing quality and quantity are beginning to hit home. Determined not to allow standards to slip and with the intention of redeveloping the Department's pedagogic practices and provision, an empirical approach to Change Management is in its early stages with an Organisational Change Strategy currently in the early stages of implementation.

In an attempt to assure collegiality and staff engagement, the first part of the strategy has been to undertake a cross-Department analysis of colleagues' perceptions of the challenges and strengths of the organisation. Somewhat ironically labelled the 'Herding Cats Study', it is part of the results of this study that form the basis of the paper. Based upon a phenomenological interpretive analysis of 48 interviews conducted over a 10 week period, this paper provides a distinctive critique of colleagues' perceptions of the positive aspects of learning and teaching within the Department.

00

2.1 The Role of Pedagogic Research & Organisational Change

The overall strategic aim of the Organisational Change Strategy is to affect a paradigm shift within the Department so that those responsible for delivering learning and teaching are viewed **by themselves and their colleagues**, managers and students as equal in status to those whose focus is research. Whilst notions of the traditional 'Engineering Academic' as being a white, middle-aged, male professor from a privileged middle or upper class background^[3] with little or no 'real-life' work or life-experience represents an inaccurate stereotype that does not apply to WMG,

the majority of those who teach within the Department hail from an industrial background. Indeed, WMG is unique in that it's highly qualified and experienced staff bring with them a depth and breadth of real-life, hard-gained work experience. Yet with pay levels in academia being below that of industry and staff-student ratios soaring exponentially over the past few years, morale has dropped and, like much of the UK H.E. Sector, many Engineering Educators in the Department perceive themselves to be under unprecedented stress with rising student demands matched by increased departmental expectations in terms of increased bureaucracy and accountability.

It is within this contested space that this Project is set.

In setting out to tackle head-on cultural changes and unrest linked with rapid growth, the need for strategically planned and delivered organisational change within the Department has come to the fore^[4,5,6]. Commencing the process of organisational change, an innovative methodological approach to capturing teachers' perspectives has been developed. Representing the first of the 10 key steps to Successful Organisational Change described by Jick (1993) (to '*Analyse the organisation and its need for change*^[7]) the success of the Herding Cats Project will be dependent on continual, authentic and honest communication between colleagues and management working together to create a shared vision of a better future.

3. METHODOLOGY

With the intention of building a solid foundation for Organisational Change, the paper authors and other colleagues from the Education Innovation Group are working across the Department to put place a number of evidence-based learning and teaching innovations and practices. To gauge the level of need through gaining a first-hand insight into staff perspectives and experiences, 48 semi-structured interviews have been conducted with teaching focused staff. Aimed at capturing colleagues' views of a number of different issues associated with all aspects of learning and teaching, student support, staff training, and organisational management an Action Research 'problem / change' based philosophy^[8] has been adopted utilising semi-structured interviews which followed a phenomenological approach.

Rooted in early 20th-century European philosophy a phenomenological approach encourages participants to express themselves through the use of 'thick' description. It involves a detailed analysis of lived experiences, purposefully seeking out individual perceptual embodiment to gain a depth of understanding of a given setting or situation^[9,10]. In terms of WMG the approach proved to be ideal as it allows for demographic variables to be set aside to guarantee anonymity of the participants whilst allowing the researcher to gain a deep understanding of the shared lived experiences of colleagues. Exposing embedded assumptions, traditions and practices, the interviews were structured so as to encourage colleagues to open up and speak freely about all aspects of their daily life as a teacher within WMG.

3.1 The Fieldwork

Adopting a purposive sampling approach^[11] eighteen senior colleagues were initially interviewed using traditional semi-structured interviews which were recorded contemporaneously before being transcribed and analysed. Based upon three core questions the interviewer encouraged colleagues to explore all aspects of their lived experiences of working within the Department. The three core questions core questions, each of which was supported by a series of prompts and sub-questions, were:

1. **What** part of your own and others' teaching practice do you feel to be of high quality?
2. **Which** aspects of teaching and learning could be improved?
3. **What** practical and pedagogical innovations could be put into place to help you improve your own teaching?

Following the initial interviews, a further thirty colleagues representing, amongst others, junior and senior lecturers, student support officers, project and personal tutors, module and course leaders were interviewed using a purposefully developed approach which, whilst being grounded in phenomenology incorporated phenomenographic visualisation^[12,13]. Each colleague was asked to draw a SWOT analysis visualising the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats they perceived to be relevant to WMG at this time. Drawing upon an approach developed by two of the three researchers^[14] in a previous study, the value of asking colleagues to draw visual images was that it immediately placed people at ease. The opportunity to discuss why they had depicted certain images and words within each of the four 'SWOT' allowed the above the three questions to be explored in considerable depth. The value of using visualised diagrammatic imaging as a methodological tool is that it allows researchers to explore in some depth the main concepts, whilst allowing the participants to express themselves in a creative and imaginative manner. Each diagram was accompanied by a key descriptive words which were then explored using the three interview questions as a framework. As before each interview was recorded contemporaneously and along with the visual images analysed utilising phenomenological techniques.

3.2 Analysis Techniques

Like all interpretive techniques, phenomenological analysis requires an iterative, inductive process whereby the data is decontextualized and re-contextualised^[15]. The first stage of the analysis involves 'decontextualization' whereby individual data was separated from its original context and coded into units of meaning. Following this, the recontextualisation of the data involved identifying codes and patterns within the units before reintegrating and organising the findings into thematic

classifications. Distilling the data into a set of classifications involved building on the process of systematic coding to allow the important elements of each participants lived experiences of the various day-to-day lived phenomena to be captured and critiqued. Methodically classifying and re-classifying the data into units addressed issues of internal and external validity with, for the third iteration, the three researchers working together to finally agree upon the main emergent themes and meanings^[16]

4. EMERGENT FINDINGS

This paper is written at a time when the analysis of data is about a third of the way through. Using the iterative and reiterative processes described above, the second iteration of the data has resulted in six distinctive classifications: Assessment & Feedback: Challenges & Weaknesses: Learning & Teaching Support Needs: Positive Practice: Student Matters: Technology Enhanced Learning.

Thus far one of these themes have been subject to third and fourth iterations allowing for the emergence of distinctive classifications and sub-topics: Positive Practice in Learning & Teaching. This paper focuses on this theme, interpreting and critiquing each theme, classifying the data into groupings which reflect colleagues' lived experiences.

4.1 Colleagues' Perceptions on Positive Practice in Learning & Teaching

4.1.1. Staff skills and experience

Undoubtedly key to the organisation's success, the skills, talents and experiences of teaching colleagues was widely discussed in the interviews with several colleagues pointing to the teaching talents of others:

Some of the teaching is brilliant. [] Some inspirational teaching where they do simulations. The Management of Change is very good. What she delivers sticks in students' minds. If we could get others to at least be as enthusiastic in their teaching, they don't have to use simulations just find their own way of engaging students.

The depth of experience in the teaching staff is remarkable, nearly all on a second career, few are on a third career. We have some really knowledgeable staff who bring a good deal of industrial experience into what they teach. This gives WMG kudos.

Many of those interviewed were confident teachers, each expressing high levels of self-awareness regarding what skills, competencies and experiences they themselves brought to the classroom:

The one thing I'm good at resource investigation. I have a workload. I like to network. I communicate well with industry and end up with a more experiential set of modules and programmes.

My strengths are coming from industry – automotive industry. I'm credible in front of an audience. I teach JLR students and am running a short course at Crewe. My colleagues are stronger in their research and academic literature. I have colleagues who are up to date on the research.

People who work in organisations and bring with them real-life experience. I bring in my own experiences and case-study learning and we try to constantly work on the blend between theory and application.

4.1.2 Pedagogic Practice

As the basis of the primary interview questions, learning and teaching practice was widely discussed throughout the interviews. For some colleagues, certain areas of the Department stood out as being examples of good practice:

Some modules are interactive; students need to be encouraged to move and change.... ..People learn by doing not listening. The way that e-business is set up – they are a perfect team. They all teach together. They have team teaching and it works really well. Each teacher has different areas of responsibility. Sometimes the modules run simultaneously, but academics don't cause any problems because they control their elective choice.

On the teaching side we have several USPs, we do stuff in small classes, which allows good team working and syndicates. The students don't like teaching in big classes

Whilst 'small group' teaching was almost universally recognised as being one of the positive practices within the Department for some colleagues the positive side of this was that it enable lecturers to build good learning relationships with students:

It's pedagogically better to teach in small groups. The fact

that we rarely have more than 30 students to teach is great for building learning relationships and engaging the students.

*The relationship between supervisor and student is a strength
We use people who know what they're talking about*

4.1.3. Evidence-Based Learning & Teaching

Across the department the concept of 'evidence-based learning and teaching' was divided into two distinctive and very different groupings; the first of which related to pedagogic research and the use of reflection and reflexivity:

*I have done pedagogic research in the past but I don't think I'll have much time to develop this any further.
But a lot of my teaching reflects on my previous pedagogical research*

My area of teaching is evidence driven. I look at two bodies of evidence. Student feedback and module reviews, chucking into Nvivo – the other is looking at journeys through the use of Moodle – trying to understand where students go, their journey

The use of such pedagogically driven evidence-based practice was very much a minority pursuit, conversely industrially experienced evidence-based practice proved to be the opposite of this, with the majority of colleagues citing the use of experience and evidence gained in industry as being central to good teaching practice:

WMG needs to use externals, experienced people from industry. To develop materials and deliver lectures

Most of what I do is for part time programmes. The externals bring a lot of experience. My modules have a lot of more external people than others. I get positive feedback from the students about this.

For some colleagues, the notion of involving industrial stakeholders was at the heart of their teaching:

I'm involved in apprenticeships. I'm managing the design... A workshop at the beginning, a small set of industrial and academic stakeholders, meant we could deliver

Such stakeholder involvement, with industry at the centre of teaching practice and content was highly regarded amongst all of the interviewees. So much so that ‘links and collaborations’ with industry represented a distinctive classification of data in itself.

4.2 Links & Collaborations with Industry

From a learning and teaching perspective, the opportunity afforded by close relations with industry meant that lectures were both credible in nature and set against a ‘real-life’ context making teaching meaningful:

On the whole we're quite traditional. We're very reliable. We have credible links into industry which enable us to contextualise what we do very well. We use people from industry a lot to make our teaching meaningful

Contacts in industry our one of our greatest strengths. We invite senior guest speakers from industry. All our tutors have a hybrid of academia and industry – this gives them credibility with the students

I'm involved heavily with [] in the new course development. The way we interact with business and allow business to drive content is positive.

One of the most striking features of colleagues’ reflections on working with industry was the strength of the academic-industrial relationships:

It's a true collaboration. Completely embedded. Both [companies]. We meet senior management every two weeks.

The course Development is ongoing. They get involved with every module, we look at the business need, and this is shaken down to course level, then expertise, and then to how we deliver.

For one colleague, the need to maximise the links with industry built within the Department’s research centres represented a source of untapped potential which could be used to enhance teaching to a far greater extent:

I'm not convinced we're fully optimising value from industry. Whether the relationship between us and WMG in research go beyond the lab and into teaching is something that we

could build on

This final idea sums up the uniqueness of WMG and in many respects reflects one of the key opportunities expressed across all of the themes, the need to make Scholarship in the Department much more than linking research and teaching through evidence-based teaching practice, but through the development of a new approach to teaching in which industry and academia work as equal partners to educate the engineering talent of the future.

5. SUMMARY DISCUSSION: IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

Encouraging colleagues to engage in discussion about their teaching is notoriously difficult^[17]. Such difficulties are augmented by the fact that in WMG, the majority of teaching staff are engineering and management professionals; mostly from industrial backgrounds where they more used to expressing themselves creatively or practically than in prose or in long reflective conversations. This unique methodological approach has been purposefully constructed so as to encourage colleagues to freely express their successes, triumphs, concerns and challenges in a non-threatening environment. By focusing on the three key interview questions and by encouraging the non-senior staff to express themselves visually before the interview began the interviews have proffered a depth of data.

As previously stated it is important to note that this paper and indeed this work represents a small part of a much larger project which is aimed at promoting and supporting a paradigm shift across all teaching in WMG; a challenge which, at this stage feels analogous to ‘Herding Cats!’ (Brown & Wareing, 2016). The driving force behind the work is a top level desire to promote high quality evidenced-based teaching whereupon individual teachers will become empowered to be reflective and reflexive practitioners, conducting their own educational research and constantly developing and evolving their own teaching practice.

The focus on the single theme *colleagues’ reflections on the positive areas of learning and teaching* provides a distinctive insight into the breadth and depth of the uniqueness of WMG itself. Whilst weaknesses and challenges will be discussed elsewhere, the decision to focus this first academic paper on the positive aspects of working in Engineering Education is not accidental. At a time when the idiosyncrasies and opaqueness of Brexit is causing uncertainty within the UK, impacting business and education alike, it is important to identify, reflect and build upon our strengths. Furthermore, whilst the whole the idea of “managing change in academia” is often viewed as an oxymoron with analogies such as ‘herding cats’ used to describe the nature of the challenge WMG has taken the bull by the horns by launching a brand new, multi-disciplinary Education Innovation Group (EIG). With a focus placed firmly on collegial support through scholarship, empirical investigation and implementation of evidence-based practice together with an ethos of leading

change through innovation in learning and teaching not only means that the time is right to begin to effect such organisational change but that people are in place to support and bolster such change as it occurs.

In conclusion, this is an exciting time to work at WMG, a unique academic-industrial department at the cutting edge of innovation, where teachers bring industrial experience and a genuine enthusiasm for applied learning. By purposefully approaching teaching in a scholarly and critical manner, innovative pedagogies will be developed, tested and disseminated. This paper is the first of many!! Watch this space as the future unfolds...

REFERENCES

- [1] WMG (2019). *WMG shaping the future*. <https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/sci/wmg/> Accessed 21/4/19
- [2] B Belfield, C., Britton, J., Dearden, L. & Van Der Erve, L., (2017). *Higher Education Funding In England: Past, Present And Options For The Future*. London. Institute for Fiscal Studies. Briefing Note Bn211. <https://www.ifs.org.uk/uploads/bn211.pdf> Accessed 21/4/19
- [3] Carter-Black, J., 2008. A Black Woman's Journey into a Predominately White Academic World. *Affilia*, 23. 2. pp.112-122.
- [4] T.D. Jick, 1993. *Managing Change & Concepts*. London. *Irwin McGraw-Hill*
- [5] J.P. Kotter, 1996. *Leading Change*. Boston. Harvard University Publications.
- [6] J.P. Kotter. (2008). *Transformation*. Leadership Excellence. 21. 1. pg. 14.
- [7] T.D. Jick. 1993. *Managing Change & Concepts*. p.195. London. *Irwin McGraw-Hill*
- [8] L. Norton. 2009. *Action Research in Teaching & Learning*. London. Routledge.
- [9] R. Sokolowski. 2000. *Introduction to Phenomenology*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press
- [10] D. Stewart & A. Mickunas. 1974. *Exploring Phenomenology: A Guide To The Field And Its Literature*. Chicago. American Library Association.

- [11] A. Bryman, 2016. *Social Research Methods*. Oxford University Press.
- [12] J. Robertson & C.H. Bond. 2001. "Experiences of the Relation between Teaching and Research: What do Academics Value?". *Higher Education Research and Development*. 20. 1. pp 5-19.
- [13] K. Trigwell, M. Prosser & P. Ginns. 2005. *Phenomenographic Pedagogy and a Revised 'Approaches to Teaching Inventory'*. *Higher Education Research and Development*. 24. 4. pp 349-360.
- [14] R. Clark & J. Andrews. 2010. "A Bridge Too Far? Breaching the research / learning and teaching nexus in a previously research-led university". In Rust, C., (Ed). *Improving Student Learning for the Twenty First Century Learner*. 2. pp 10-21, Oxford. Oxford Brookes University Publications
- [15] L. Ayres, K. Kavanaugh & K.A. Knafel. 2003. Within-case and across-case approaches to qualitative data analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*, 13, 871-883.
- [16] J.W. Creswell. 1997. *Qualitative Inquiry And Research Design: Choosing Among Five Traditions*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [17] R. Clark & J. Andrews 2017. *Engineering or The Engineer? A Paradox of Practice*. In *New Approaches to Engineering in Higher Education*. London. Institute of Engineering & Technology. Engineering Professors Council. <http://epc.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/New-Approaches-Conference-Proceedings-book-final.pdf> 9/2/19
- [18] S. Brown, S. & S. Wareing. 2016. Academic Development and Senior Management. *Advancing Practice in Academic Development*, pp.258-272.